

Experimental study on vibration characteristics of sandwich beams with aluminum skins and magnetorheological elastomer cores

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SUMMARY

Magnetorheological elastomer (MRE) material consisting of a natural or synthetic rubber filled with micron sized iron particles is a smart material whose properties can be controlled by a magnetic field. In this paper, experimental study on the dynamic characteristics of an MRE core embedded sandwich beam is carried out. Frequency responses from experimental results on MRE cored sandwich beams are obtained from samples placed in a specially designed test rig. The dynamic responses are characterised and localised magnetic field effects, boundary condition effects and damping effects are analysed. MRE cored sandwich beams with aluminium skins offer potentially advantageous features of adaptiveness of dynamic properties for vibration reductions.

Key words: Magnetorheological elastomer (MRE), forced vibration test, permanent magnet, smart structures, MRE cored sandwich structures.

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1 Introduction

Magnetorheological (MR) material consists of micron sized magnetically permeable particles suspended in a non-magnetic medium (e.g., fluid, elastomer). The properties of such materials can be changed and controlled by variation in the presence of magnetic field. Research in the field of MR materials was initiated in the late 1940s [1]. In recent years their potential capability has been increasingly recognised as semi active control devices in car suspensions, buildings and bridges. MR Elastomer (MRE) is composed of natural or synthetic rubber and iron particles. When a liquid state rubber combined with ferrous particles is exposed to a steady magnetic field, the ferrous particles form chain-like structures arranged along the magnetic field during the curing process. MRE is a durable material with variable stiffness and damping properties and can be operated in severe temperatures (-50°C to 150°C) with low voltage supplies. The properties of MRE are affected by the volume fraction of the magnetic particles in the elastomer and the relative size and alignment of the particles after cure.

MRE has been used in applications where stiffness or resonance changes are needed [2]. For example, an MRE tuned vibration absorber (TVA) device can modify a mechanical systems response against external disturbances through activating an internal

electromagnetic field. Consequently, unexpected vibrational or impact energy can be dissipated through activation of the MRE material via a closed loop control system.

Performance of MRE can be enhanced by using different combinations of materials or through varied experimental and practical schemes. The optimal particle volume fraction of magnetic particles for the largest stiffness change was predicted to be about 27% to 30% by numerical means [3] and proved with experiment [4, 5]. It has been reported that MRE with large irregular iron particles have a large MR effect although the particles need not be aligned within the material [6]. However the rheological properties of the matrix material do not influence the MR effect. It has been also reported that cyclic loading conditions with different strain amplitudes manifest a dependence of the viscoelastic storage modulus with the maximum stiffness change being up to more than twice in the audible frequency range [7]. The maximum percentage of change in modulus being observed is in the vicinity of 1-2% strain [2, 8]. An MRE tuned vibration absorber (TVA) system can be developed with minimal engineering design changes to meet other potential applications such as automotive bushing to enhance ride quality [9]. Deng *et al.* [10] carried out the dynamic tests for MREs as adaptive tuned vibration absorbers. It was shown that the MRE TVA achieves a frequency change up to 147% with 60dB absorption of frequency response. Furthermore, MRE TVA is fail-safe because the system will continue to manage the device as a passive isolator in the event of power system failure.

Sandwich configured structures are used where high stiffness / weight and strength / weight ratios are required. The flexural stiffness of a sandwich beam is proportional to $d^2h/4$, where d and h are the thickness of the core material and skin respectively. Due to the high stiffness which results in a higher natural frequency, the number of responding modes is drastically reduced. The transverse shear interaction between skins and core material is also an important factor in the vibration response of a sandwich beam with a soft core, which induces the damping for sandwich structure with viscoelastic cores. MR material has been used to carry out vibration analysis to observe vibration responses in real time and vibration suppression capabilities of three layered MR adaptive sandwich beams [11, 12]. It was shown that the vibration minimization capabilities of MR adaptive structures are significant. The development of MRE based adaptive structure was initiated only very recently. Zhou & Wang [13] carried out theoretical study on MRE embedded smart sandwich beams with non-conductive skins based on higher order sandwich panel theory. However the damping effect of the sandwich beam has not been investigated. Demchuk & Kuz'min (2002) measured the elastic modulus and loss factor using clamped vibrating sandwich beam. It was shown that there is a pronounced MRE effect when nonaligned magnetorheological elastomer with the large sized iron particles is used.

The aim of this study therefore is to investigate the dynamic characteristics of an MRE adapted sandwich beam in terms of amplitude of force, boundary effect and damping effect under various combinations of magnetic field. To this end, a forced vibration test rig has been developed, which allows application of a magnetic field through the height of the beam.

2 Experimental Setup

The experimental study is carried out to illustrate the control capabilities of MRE adaptive sandwich structures in real time, and to assess the dependence of frequency response and the damping upon a magnetic field.

The MRE core specimens are made of room temperature vulcanizing (RTV) silicone (Elastosil M4644, Wacker Co.) including catalyst and 3-5 micron sized iron powder particles (CIP CC, BASF). The amount of iron particles is 30 vol %. The first step is to mix iron powders with RTV silicone for 10 minutes to achieve even dispersion and then air bubbles are pulled out in a vacuum chamber. After pouring the mixture into an aluminium mould, the curing process is conducted between two permanent magnetic poles for 24 hours in order to increase MRE performance. Two magnetic distributors attached to both ends of permanent magnet are made of a cast iron in order to distribute magnetic field strength to along the length of the beam evenly. A measured magnetic field strength of along the surface of the distributor is 0.3 Tesla. Finally, the cured MRE core is bonded to two steel skins with the aid of epoxy glue (Araldite 2015).

Table 1 Properties of materials consisting sandwich beam

Material	Density (g/cm ³)	Shear Modulus (MPa)	Elastic Modulus (GPa)	Material Damping (η)
Aluminium	2.5	-	60	-
MRE (0 Tesla)	3.1	2.5	-	0.13
(0.3 Tesla)	3.1	4.7	-	0.17

Table 1 lists the properties of the aluminum skins and MRE core. The shear moduli of MRE are measured at 0.1% strain statically using electric testing instrument (Instron ElectroPlus E1000) with and without presence of electromagnetic field respectively. The MRE adaptive sandwich beam used in the tests consists of two aluminium skins and MRE core material. The dimensions of the MRE core and the aluminium skins are 230×20×10 mm³ and 230×20×0.5 mm³, respectively. The forced vibration test rig consists of ten pieces of permanent magnets (N35 Block Magnet, MMG Magnet Ltd.) as shown in Fig. 1. Each magnet is bonded to the nonmagnetic stainless steel block for 24 hours. Stainless blocks are bolted to the aluminium back plates in order to mount and remove easily for experimental purpose. The size of each magnet is 42.0×24.0×12.5 mm³ in order to maintain enough magnetic field strength. A 4 mm air gap between the magnet faces and the skins of the sandwich beam which allows a stinger of shaker to pass through and fix to the surface of the sandwich beam without any other contact. The frame is made of aluminium to prevent dissipation of magnetic field strength. Two aluminium back plates are mounted to the guided rails which allow back plates to adjust air gap between two sides of magnets by bolting. The default air gap between each side of magnet faces is 10 mm of which magnetic field strength is measured to be about 0.3 Tesla.

Figure 1 Forced vibration test rig (① permanent magnets, ② aluminium back plate, ③ shaker, ④ aluminium frame, ⑤ MRE cored sandwich beam)

For an idealised simply supported beam, difficulties may arise in satisfying all of the requirements under experimental conditions. The following requirements for simply supported boundary conditions were satisfied in the design (Yalcintas & Dai, 2004): (1) the transverse displacement is zero at each end; (2) the moment is zero at each end; (3) axial force of the beam is zero and therefore the longitudinal displacement is free of constraint. In order to satisfy these conditions, one end of beam is supported by hinged bearing pin while the other end is supported by wedge shaped chamfer. The vertical displacement of the rolling pins was fixed while the longitudinal displacement is free. The pins could rotate freely, which satisfied the second requirement. This will reduce a coupling effect from the vibration response caused by extra structures such as aluminium frame. Forced vibration test consists of a test rig, a shaker (Ling Dynamics Systems V101), a PZT accelerometer (PCB352C22), a signal generator (Data Physics Quattro), a controller, an analyser and an amplifier. When the shaker applies the input force to the structure, the PZT accelerometer measures the structural response. A signal generator produces a swept sine wave range from 0 to 1000 Hz in 1 Hz increments. A force signal received from the signal generator is varied by varying current. The PZT accelerometer is used to measure the vibrational acceleration at a single point. The stinger of the shaker is bonded to the bottom surface of the beam at a location of 138 mm ($3L/5$) from the left end of the beam while the accelerometer is attached to the top surface of the beam at a location of 46 mm ($L/5$) from the left end of the beam.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Localised magnetic field effect

Fig. 5 shows a comparison the comparison of the damping change under a localised magnetic field with different arrangement such as three pairs of magnets fitted in the middle (OMMMO) and evenly distributed (MOMOM) for simply supported and clamped sandwich beam, where 'M' stands for a pair of magnetic fields applied

while 'O' stands for a pair of void area. Change in damping ratio for the former case is more significant than that for the latter case. The magnetic preload effect for simply supported beam is much more than that for clamped beam. The results show that large damping effect happens when the magnetic fields are applied in the middle rather than the near of the boundaries.

Figure 5 Comparison of frequency response of aluminium MRE embedded sandwich beam for different boundary conditions with three pair of different location of magnets

Fig. 6 (a) shows the damping changes with two pairs of magnets arrayed evenly along the beam (OMOMO) with different poles and same poles for the clamped beam. Due to the limit number of permanent magnets only two pair of magnets is mounted in this test. Compared to the fully embedded magnets along the beam's length, the effect of damping changes are less significant. However, the damping changes shows difference between magnet arrays with same and different poles. When the magnets are arrayed with same poles, the damping effect is significant even if the same number of magnets is used. Fig. 6 (b) shows the comparison of damping change with two pairs of magnets arrayed at both ends (MOOOM) with different poles and same poles for the clamped beam. Compared two figures, higher damping change can be seen in the case of OMOMO at first two modes. These indicate that the damping effects are less obvious when the magnetic fields are applied near of the boundaries.

Figure 6 Comparison of damping changes of clamped MRE embedded sandwich beams with same and different poles

3.2 Effect of different boundary conditions of sandwich beam

Fig. 2 shows the comparison of frequency response of MRE embedded sandwich beam with different boundary condition. The frequency change of clamped beam in Fig. 3 (b) is bigger than that of simply supported beam in Fig. 3 (a). However, most of resonance peaks decrease at whole frequency ranges for simply supported beam when the magnetic fields are applied to the structures. Conversely, the change of peak amplitude for the clamped beam is much less than that for simply supported beam. The results indicate that the energy dissipation of simply supported beam is obvious because energy dissipation is caused by flexibility from the interface of the core and aluminium skins.

Figure 2 Comparison of frequency response of MRE embedded sandwich beam with different boundary conditions

The fundamental frequencies are shifted to lower frequency in the presence of magnetic field. This is due to the magnetic preload which is assumed to be at a low frequency (Yin *et al.*, 2006). Since the force is applied at nodal point, small peak response appears at mode 5.

3.3 Effect of different air gap

Another aspect is the effect of magnetic field strength by adjusting air gap between permanent magnets and faces. The strength of magnetic field changes from 0.3 to 0.35 Tesla by varying of air gap from 10 to 5 mm. The comparison of frequency response of clamped MRE embedded sandwich beam with different air gap is shown in Fig. 3. The first resonance frequency of 5 mm air gap is shifted to lower frequency about 37 % while that of 10 mm air gap is not changed. The damping ratio is determined by using half power bandwidth method for each mode given as $\xi = (\omega_+ - \omega_-) / \omega_n$, where ω_+ and ω_- are the corresponding frequencies to the 2dB reduction, ω_n is the resonance frequency. The damping ratio of the first mode of 5 mm air gap is 0.15 while that of 10 mm air gap is 0.08. From the second mode to higher modes, the damping ratio of 5 mm air gap is higher than that of 10 mm air gap. The results show that the magnetic field affects frequency changes as well as damping effect. At lower frequency ranges, the

magnetic preload effect is more obvious when the air gap between beam and magnets is smaller.

Figure 3 Comparison of frequency response of clamped MRE embedded sandwich beam with different air gap

3.4 Effect of different forces applying

Since material behaviour of rubber-like MRE materials is nonlinear, it causes different value of vibrational energy dissipation. Thus, the effect of applying force amplitude to observe damping effect is investigated. The range of the force amplitude ratio (f / f_{ref}) is applied from 1 to 10, where f and f_{ref} are the applying force and the reference force, respectively. Fig. 4 shows the change of damping ratio in terms of various force amplitudes. Obvious damping changes are shown at first mode. Big damping change can be seen when the force amplitude ratio (f / f_{ref}) is 10. From second mode to higher mode, damping values drop down quickly and even lower than that of without magnetic field when the force amplitude ratio is 1. From the amplitude ratio of 5 to higher, when magnetic fields are applied damping effect is higher than that of without magnetic field. The results confirm that when the amplitude of force oscillation increases the energy dissipation for the fundamental frequency increases. It seems that the magnetic force affects not only change of property of core material but also change of inertia effect of the beam structure. These phenomena occur when the magnetic force is strong enough, which induce large shear stress at the interfaces between MRE core and aluminium skins.

(a) $f / f_{ref} = 1$

(b) $f / f_{ref} = 5$

(c) $f / f_{ref} = 10$

Figure 4 Comparison of damping ratio of clamped aluminum MRE embedded sandwich beam with different amplitude of input force (5mm air gap)

4 Conclusions

Comprehensive experimental forced vibrational analysis of MRE embedded sandwich beam are investigated with various aspects. Forced vibration tests with different magnetic field strength, distribution, oscillation of force amplitudes and boundary conditions are carried out to examine dynamic behaviour of MRE core embedded sandwich beam. It was observed that the combination of magnets and polarity definitely affect to the characteristics of MRE core embedded sandwich structure. Obvious damping effect was observed when beam is simply supported and when the air gap between the magnet faces and the skins of the sandwich beam is reduced. It was also observed that the change of structural damping is dependent not on frequency ranges but on external force and the strength of magnetic field. Moreover, localised magnetic effect corresponds to certain frequency ranges. Ongoing work on MRE embedded sandwich beams will investigate dynamic characteristics of different topologies of sandwich structures. Overall, MRE adaptive sandwich beams can be used where vibrational isolation and damping is needed for vibration suppression.

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References

1. RABINOW, J. 1948. The magnetic fluid clutch. *AIEE Trans.*, **67**, 1308–1315.
2. JOLLY, M.R., BENDER, J.W., & CARLSON, J.D. 1999. Properties and Applications of Commercial Magnetorheological Fluids. *J. Intelligent Material System and Structures*, **10(1)**, 5–13.
3. DAVIS, L.C. 1998. Model of magnetorheological elastomers. *Journal of Applied Physics*, **85(6)**, 3348–3351.
4. DEMCHUK, S.A., & KUZ'MIN, V.A. 2002. Viscoelastic properties of magnetorheological elastomers in the regime of dynamic deformation. *Journal of Engineering Physics and Thermophysics*, **75(2)**, 396–400.
5. CHOI, W. J., XIONG, Y. P., & SHENOI, R. A. 2008. Characterisation of magnetorheological elastomer materials for the core of smart sandwich structures. *8th International Conference on Sandwich Structures*, 818–826.
6. LOKANDER, M., & STENBERG, B. 2003. Performance of isotropic magnetorheological rubber materials. *Polymer Testing*, **22(3)**, 245–251.
7. BLOM, P., & KARI, L. 2005. Amplitude and frequency dependence of magneto-sensitive rubber in a wide frequency range. *Polymer Testing*, **24(5)**, 656–662.
8. STEPANOV, G.V., ABRAMCHUK, S.S., GRISHIN, D.A., NIKITIN, L.V., KRAMARENKO, E.Y., & KHOKHLOV, A.R. 2007. Effect of a homogeneous magnetic field on the viscoelastic behavior of magnetic elastomers. *Polymer*, **48(2)**, 488–495.

9. GINDER, J.M., NICHOLS, M.E., ELIE, L.D., & CLARK, S.M. 2000. Controllable stiffness components based on magnetorheological elastomers. 418–425 of: *Wereley, N.M. (ed. Smart and Materials 2000: Smart Structures and Integrated Systems, Proceedings of SPIE 3985)*.
10. DENG, H, GONG, X, & WANG, L. 2006. Development of an adaptive tuned vibration absorber with magnetorheological elastomer. *Smart Materials and Structures*, **15(5)**, N111–N116.
11. SUN, Q., ZHOU, J., & ZHANG, L. 2003. An adaptive beam model and dynamic characteristics of magnetorheological materials. *Journal of Sound and Vibration*, **261(3)**, 465–481.
12. YALCINTAS, M, & DAI, H. 2004. Vibration suppression capabilities of magnetorheological materials based adaptive structures. *Smart Materials and Structures*, **13**, 1–11.
13. ZHOU, G.Y., & WANG, Q. 2005. Magnetrorheological elastomer-based smart sandwich beams with nonconductive skins. *Smart Mater. Struct*, **14**, 1001–1009.